

Code Legibility Survey

You are about to answer a questionnaire about source code readability for a research project conducted in collaboration between

. Your participation is voluntary, and your data will be kept confidential and used only for the purpose of this research. We thank you for your participation!

Some demographic information will be asked initially, and providing your email for further contact is optional. After that, you will go through 15 questions to compare the readability of two code snippets. To complete the entire questionnaire should take from 10 to 15 minutes. Please, agree with the term below to continue.

- I agree with the usage of the data provided in this questionnaire for research purposes.

In case of doubts or suggestions contact us:

PART I - Demographic information

Main occupation:

- Student
- Professional developer
- Researcher
- Other

Highest completed education level (or equivalent) :

- No formal education
- High school
- Technical training
- Undergraduate degree
- Master's degree
- Ph.D.

Country you currently reside:

Gender identity:

- Man
- Woman
- Non- binary
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to self describe

Age:

- 18 to 24
- 25 to 34
- 35 to 44
- 45 to 54
- 55 to 64
- Over 64
- Prefer not to say

In which programming languages do you consider yourself proficient?

- Assembly
- C#
- C
- C++
- Java
- JavaScript
- Go
- Kotlin
- Perl
- PHP
- Python
- R
- Ruby
- Rust
- Scala
- Swift
- Others

How many years of **coding** experience do you have?

- less than 1
- 1to 2
- 2 to 3
- 3 to 5
- 5 to 10
- 10 to 20
- 20+

How experienced are you in **Java**?

- Novice
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

How familiar are you with using **annotations** for existing APIs and frameworks?

Annotations = "annotation" in Java, "attributes" in C#, "decorators" or "tags" in other languages.

- Not familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Extremely familiar

How many APIs/ Frameworks that use annotations have you already used?

- None
- Few (1 or 2)
- Some (3 to 5)
- Several (5 to 10)
- Many (10 or more)

What is your current familiarity with creating new code annotations and developing code that reads them using reflection?

- Not familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Extremely familiar

If you are willing to be contacted for a follow-up conversation, please provide us your email:

Two code snippets will be presented for each question. You will compare them in terms of **code readability**.

The following are an example of 2 code snippets that are similar to the ones that you will need to compare in terms of readability in this survey:

```
1 public class Character extends Serializable{
2     //class body omitted
3 }
4
```

CODE A

```
1 @Serializable
2 public class Character{
3     //class body omitted
4 }
```

CODE B

Please, read and confirm the following statements before continuing:

- I am aware that the code snippets presented for each question have the same behavior and will produce the same result when executed.
- I am aware that I will compare the code snippets considering only their readability.
- I am aware that I don't need to understand precisely what the code does.

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1  public class Person{
2
3      private double height;
4
5      private String name;
6
7      private int age;
8
9      public List<Difference> compare(Person p){
10         Comparator c = new Comparator(Person.class);
11         c.addNumericTolerance("height",0.01);
12         c.ignoreInComparison("age");
13         return c.compare(this, p);
14     }
15 }
```

CODE A

```
1  public class Person{
2
3      @NumericTolerance(0.01)
4      private double height;
5
6      private String name;
7
8      @IgnoreInComparison
9      private int age;
10
11     public List<Difference> compare(Person p){
12         Comparator c = new Comparator(Person.class);
13         return c.compare(this, p);
14     }
15 }
```

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class EvaluationComponent{
2
3     public void evaluateProduct(Product p, Comment c){
4         //method body
5         if(sucess){
6             Gamification.addPointsToUser(CurrentUser.get(), 10);
7         }
8     }
9 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class EvaluationComponent{
2
3     @AddPointsToUserOnSuccess(10)
4     public void evaluateProduct(Product p, Comment c){
5         //method body
6     }
7 }
8
9
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class CommentManager{
2
3     public void excludeComment(Comment c){
4         SecurityComponent.verifyUserRole("admin");
5         //method body
6     }
7 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class CommentManager{
2
3     @VerifyUserRole("admin");
4     public void excludeComment(Comment c){
5         //method body
6     }
7 }
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class InterfaceHandler{
2
3     public void handleClick(MouseEvent e){
4         if(e.numberOfClicks() == 2 and e.componentName().equals("OK_button")){
5             //execute logic
6         }
7     }
8 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class InterfaceHandler{
2
3     @OnMouseEvent(numberOfClicks=2, componentName="OK_button")
4     public void handleClick(){
5         //execute logic
6     }
7 }
8 }
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class SocialServiceIntegration{
2
3     public UserData retrieveUserData(String idNumber){
4         try{
5             SocialServiceInvoker ssi = new SocialServiceInvoker();
6             return ssi.getUserInfo(idNumber);
7         } catch(ExternalInvocationException ex){
8             handleError(ex);
9         }
10    }
11
12    public void handleErrors(Exception ex){
13        //error handling
14    }
15 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class SocialServiceIntegration{
2
3     public UserData retrieveUserData(String idNumber){
4         SocialServiceInvoker ssi = new SocialServiceInvoker();
5         return ssi.getUserInfo(idNumber);
6     }
7
8     @ExceptionHandler(ExternalInvocationException.class)
9     public void handleErrors(Exception ex){
10        //error handling
11    }
12 }
```

CODE B

CODE A Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1  public class BuyController{
2
3      private ShoppingCart cart = Session.get("cart");
4
5      public addItem(Product product){
6          cart.add(product);
7      }
8
9      public removeItem(Product product){
10         cart.remove(product);
11     }
12
13 }
```

CODE A

```
1  public class BuyController{
2
3      @Session
4      private ShoppingCart cart;
5
6      public addItem(Product product){
7          cart.add(product);
8      }
9
10     public removeItem(Product product){
11         cart.remove(product);
12     }
13
14 }
```

CODE B

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class Parameters{
2
3     private long timeout;
4
5     private String filename;
6
7     private boolean verbose;
8
9     public static void main(String[] args){
10         ParamMapper mapper = new ParamMapper();
11         mapper.addTextParameter("file", "filename");
12         mapper.addNumericParameter("timeout", "timeout");
13         mapper.verifyParameterPresence("verbose", "verbose");
14         Parameters p = mapper.map(Parameters.class);
15         //software logic
16     }
17
18 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class Parameters{
2
3     @NumericValue
4     private long timeout;
5
6     @TextValue(name="file")
7     private String filename;
8
9     @IsParameterPresent
10    private boolean verbose;
11
12    public static void main(String[] args){
13        ParamMapper mapper = new ParamMapper();
14        Parameters p = mapper.map(Parameters.class);
15        //software logic
16    }
```

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1  public class User{
2
3      private String id;
4
5      private String login;
6
7      public String toXML(){
8          XMLConverter xc = new XMLConverter();
9          xc.mapAttributeToElement("id","identifier");
10         xc.mapAttributeToElement("login","username");
11         return xc.toXML(this)
12     }
13 }
```

CODE A

```
1  public class User{
2
3      @XMLElement("identifier")
4      private String id;
5
6      @XMLElement("username")
7      private String login;
8
9      public String toXML(){
10         XMLConverter xc = new XMLConverter();
11         return xc.toXML(this)
12     }
13 }
```

CODE B

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class ScheduleSystem{
2
3     public scheduleTask(Task t, Date date){
4         AlertManager am = ComponentFactory.getImplementation(AlertManager.class);
5         am.createAlert(date, t.getDescription());
6         //additional logic
7     }
8 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class ScheduleSystem{
2
3     @Inject
4     AlertManager am;
5
6     public scheduleTask(Task t, Date date){
7         am.createAlert(date, t.getDescription());
8         //additional logic
9     }
10 }
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class ExternalServices{
2
3     public init(){
4         ServicePublisher sp = new ServicePublisher();
5         sp.addService(this,"getProductData","product", "get");
6         sp.addService(this,"setProductData","product", "set");
7         sp.publish();
8     }
9
10    public String getProductData(){
11        //methodbody
12    }
13
14    public void setProductData(String data){
15        //methodbody
16    }
17 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class ExternalServices{
2
3     public init(){
4         ServicePublisher sp = new ServicePublisher();
5         sp.addServices(this);
6         sp.publish();
7     }
8
9     @ServiceURL(base="product",name="get")
10    public String getProductData(){
11        //methodbody
12    }
13
14    @ServiceURL(base="product",name="set")
15    public void setProductData(String data){
16        //methodbody
17    }
```

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1  public class Product{
2
3      private Integer id;
4
5      private String name;
6
7      private String barcode;
8
9      public boolean isValid(){
10         Validator v = new Validator();
11         v.fieldNotNull("id");
12         v.fieldNotEmpty("name");
13         v.fieldLengthRange("name",5,20);
14         v.fieldRegularExpression("barcode","^[8]{1}[0-9]{11}$");
15         return v.validate(this);
16     }
17 }
```

CODE A

```
1  public class Product{
2
3      @NotNull
4      private Integer id;
5
6      @NotEmpty
7      @LengthRange(min=5, max=20)
8      private String name;
9
10     @RegularExpression("^[8]{1}[0-9]{11}$")
11     private String barcode;
12
13     public boolean isValid(){
14         Validator v = new Validator();
15         return v.validate(this);
16     }
17 }
```

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class Airplane implements Persistent{
2
3     public static final boolean sessionScope = true;
4
5 }
```

CODE A

```
1 @SessionScope
2 @Persistent
3 public class Airplane{
4
5 }
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class Product implements ObjectLoader{
2
3     @Override
4     public void loadObject(String filename){
5         //loading logic
6         cleanCache();
7     }
8
9     public void cleanCache(){
10        //clear the cache data
11    }
12 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class Product implements ObjectLoader{
2
3     @Override
4     public void loadObject(String filename){
5         //loading logic
6     }
7
8     @AfterLoad
9     public void cleanCache(){
10        //clear the cache data
11    }
12 }
```

CODE B

👉 CODE A Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class FinancialOperation{
2
3     private TransactionManager tm;
4
5     public void transferMoney(Account source, Account destiny, double amount){
6         tm.initTransaction();
7         //method body
8         tm.finishTransaction();
9     }
10 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class FinancialOperation{
2
3     @Transactional
4     public void transferMoney(Account source, Account destiny, double amount){
5         //method body
6     }
7 }
8
9
10
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Compare the **readability** of the two code snippets considering that they generate a similar behavior.

```
1 public class BusinessComponent{
2
3     private Connection c;
4
5     public BusinessComponent(){
6         c = DriverManager.getConnection("jdbc:oracle:dbhost.dbname","user","password");
7     }
8 }
```

CODE A

```
1 public class BusinessComponent{
2
3     @Connection(url="jdbc:oracle:dbhost.dbname",user="user",password="password");
4     private Connection c;
5
6     public BusinessComponent(){
7     }
8 }
```

CODE B

- CODE A Definitely More Readable
- CODE A Slightly More Readable
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE A
- Similar Readability, but prefer CODE B
- CODE B Slightly More Readable
- CODE B Definitely More Readable

Considering the code snippets presented before, how do you think the use of annotations (@ ...) affects the **code's readability**? (you can answer in Portuguese or English)

Do you have any other comments for us? (you can answer in Portuguese or English)

Thank you for answering our survey! We hope that you've learned about code annotations while reflecting on the legibility of code snippets.

We kindly ask that you send the link to our survey to other programmers that you know:

If you have any questions, don't hesitate to contact us at

